

FUZZY LOGIC-BASED PATH PLANNING FOR AUTONOMOUS MOBILE ROBOTS: A NOVEL APPROACH TO ENHANCED NAVIGATION

Ahmed Al-areqi⁵, Róbert Szabolcsi⁶

Abstract

With advancements in artificial intelligence technology, robots have been deployed across various sectors, becoming integral to the fabric of intelligent, technology-driven cities designed to reduce human error. Robots are composed of hardware and software, interacting in real-time to achieve seamless functionality. The software infrastructure of autonomous robots encompasses planning, control, and design processes, all of which must operate concurrently to enable the Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) to reach its designated destination. AMRs encounter complex environments in real-world applications, particularly in motion planning and control. Path planning, a significant challenge for AMRs, often involves navigating various path shapes and curvatures, including Clothoid, Polynomial, and Spline curves. This paper aims to develop a kinematic model of an AMR in MATLAB[®]. Subsequently, a Fuzzy logic controller will be integrated, enabling autonomous movement based on reference points within a static environment. Finally, A path planning algorithm will be implemented to assess key factors such as safety, efficiency, and overall performance of the algorithm.

Keywords

Mobile Robots, Path Planning, Fuzzy logic, MATLAB[®]

1 Introduction

Robotics is an interdisciplinary field that integrates diverse disciplines spanning mechanical, electrical, and electronics engineering, computer vision, cognitive science, and social sciences. Today, it has emerged as one of the most advanced domains of scientific research. Mobile robots, owing to their capabilities in surveillance, planetary exploration, patrolling, emergency rescue operations, reconnaissance, petrochemical applications, industrial automation, construction, entertainment, museum guidance, personal services, extreme environment intervention, transportation, household tasks, and more, are increasingly capable of replacing humans in a wide array of industrial and nonindustrial contexts. (Rubio et al.,2019)

Autonomous mobile robots can operate under manual control (e.g., in surveillance or underwater operations) or autonomously (e.g., in planetary exploration), relying entirely on sensor-based perception to interpret their environment. Robots utilize a perception system for fully autonomous operation to analyse sensory data, make decisions, and execute actions. A centralized control system is essential to coordinate the robot's subsystems, serving as the foundational framework for practical autonomous functionality. The core components of mobile robotics include locomotion, perception, cognition, and navigation, which collectively enable adaptive and intelligent behaviour. (Siegwart, Nourbakhsh, & Scaramuzza, 2011)

⁵ Óbuda University Bánki Donát, Doctoral School on Safety and Security Sciences Budapest, Népszínház u. 8, 1081,Ahmedalareqi2020@outlook.com

⁶ Óbuda University / Institute of Electronic and Communication Systems, Kandó Kálmán Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Department of Measurement Technology and Automation, 17 Tavaszmező Str., Room T.C.403, H-1084, Budapest, Hungary, szabolcsi.robort@kvk.uni-obuda.hu.

Locomotion forms the foundational domain of mobile robotics, encompassing kinematic and dynamic models that govern the robot's movement mechanisms. This field also integrates control theory and controller design to regulate motion. The perception system recognizes and analyzes environmental signals—such as sound, light, and visual data—through sensor technologies, enabling the robot to interpret its surroundings. Cognition involves processing sensor-derived input data, synthesizing actionable decisions, and transmitting commands to the controller to fulfil the robot's operational objectives. Finally, navigation represents the most critical capability in autonomous robotics, as it integrates artificial intelligence and machine learning theories, including motion planning, path planning algorithms, and learning paradigms such as supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. (M. Ceccarelli and F. Kececi,2015)

Among various types of mobile robots, differential drive mobile robot (DDMR) is one of the most used structures in academic study. It consists of a chassis with two fixed wheels that are driven by independent electric motors controlled by a microcontroller. Every wheel is perpendicular to the ground, which means the contact between the ground and the wheels is non-slipping and rolling less (S. Crowe.,2020).

The area of automatic motion planning is the most significant challenge confronting autonomous robotics. Motion planning is a computational problem involving recognizing a sequence of valid configurations that moves the object from the start goal to the destination through obstacles. The goal is to automatically translate a task in a high-level language into a set of low-level motion steps, or feedback controllers, to achieve the task.

The primary objective of this class of computational problems is to determine the shortest feasible path for a robotic system—whether a robotic arm, mobile robot, or even a magically free-flying piano—to transition from an initial configuration to a target configuration while avoiding obstacles. Additionally, motion planning, as a field, has evolved to address a vast array of problem variations and now encompasses diverse applications such as: Digital character animation, Surgical procedure planning, and Automated verification of factory layouts.(C. Myint, N. N. J. I. J. o. S. Win,2016).

Since the 1970s, research has focused on solving the complications of path planning, starting with sample problems such as moving a mobile robot from point A to point B with no obstacles and finishing with very complex environments with various obstacles. Path planning algorithms could be applied in a fully known environment where the map is regularly upgraded by the implemented sensors such as LiDAR, RADAR, and ultrasound. These sensors produce an approximately real map.

There are two methods of path planning algorithms that are categorized based on the environment, whether a global or local map. Global path planning is the process in which all the information about the surrounding environment is entirely determined to achieve the optimal path from the starting point to the destination. In contrast, local path planning deals with unknown and dynamic environments. In this method, data must be uploaded in real time to be processed by the path planning algorithms.

This means the algorithm is performed while the robot moves and updates data. Robot with local path planning can respond to any change within the environment by analyzing, executing, and creating a new path (Wikipedia,2022)

Fig. path planning problem

Source: (GEO.SPATIAL INFORMATION SCIENCE, 2018)

1.1 Path planning

Path planning is finding the optimal path from the starting point to the destination. It is used in robotics to make robots decide their paths based on input data of the surrounding environment. Many path planning algorithms are included in robotics, such as A visibility graph based on the A* algorithm, Wave propagation, Potential field, and Probabilistic Road Map. Each algorithm has different features and specifications regarding execution time, path length between the starting point and the target, and the safety factor of the robot.

Artificial intelligence was introduced to assist in figuring out the complications in motion planning by searching for a sequence of logical operators or actions that shift an initial world state into the desired goal state (Lynch & Park, 2023). Research on motion planning is initially focusing on finding a complete and appropriate path algorithm.

These algorithms could execute if they terminate indefinitely and return a valid solution or fail otherwise (Yang, et al., 2019). Path planning has many aspects, such as crossing between obstacles and coordinating the movement of a group of robots on land or in the sky. So, the main point of path planning is to determine a suitable path that takes less time to execute and is low-cost to achieve the intended task.

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Path planning algorithms could be applied in a fully known environment where the implemented sensors such as LiDAR, RADAR, and ultrasound regularly upload the map. These sensors produce an approximately accurate map. Two methods of path planning algorithms are categorized based on the environment, whether a global or local map (Carbone & Gomez-Barvo, 2015). As shown in Fig. 2

Fig. 2: Types of path planning

Source: (GEO.SPATIAL INFORMATION SCIENCE, 2018)

Global path planning is a method in which complete prior knowledge of the surrounding environment is utilized to determine an optimal path from a starting point to a destination. In contrast, local path planning operates in unknown or dynamic environments. In this approach, the planning algorithms must continuously update and process real-time sensor data. These algorithms operate dynamically as the robot navigates, adjusting to environmental changes by analyzing sensory inputs, executing decisions, and regenerating paths as needed. Robots equipped with local path planning can thus adapt to unexpected obstacles or alterations in their surroundings.

Geometric path planning involves generating collision-free geometric paths for mobile robots. Algorithms designed for applications such as vacuum cleaning or lawn mowing enable robots to maneuver around obstacles while prioritizing routes that minimize time and energy consumption, optimizing task efficiency.

Based on their methodologies, geometric path planning algorithms are categorized into three primary approaches for generating paths: the roadmap technique, the cell decomposition algorithm, and the artificial potential method. (Carbone & Gomez-Barvo, 2015).

The Configuration Space, shown in Figure 3, is defined as the place where path planning algorithms are implemented. In other words, it is a space that has all possible mobile robot configurations.

There are three definitions that can be presented: the configuration space (C—space), the space of free configuration (F—space), and the representation of obstacles in the environment (C—Obs). The (q) represents the specification of the mobile robot's position and orientation with reference to a fixed reference frame (f) (LaValle, 2006).

Fig.3: Configuration Space of Robot

Source: (Safe and Interactive Robotics,2017)

1.2 Fuzzy logic controller

Fuzzy logic is a way in which our brains classify or analyze different situations, such as the variation in color shades—blue, light blue, dark blue, and so on. A similar technique is used in neural networks, expert systems, and other artificial intelligence applications.

Fuzzy logic is essential for developing human-like capabilities in AI, sometimes called artificial general intelligence. This involves representing generalized human cognitive abilities in software, enabling an AI system to find a solution when faced with an unfamiliar task. (Zhao, Blaabjerg, & Wang, 2021).

Fuzzy logic is essential in control systems due to its ability to handle uncertain and imprecise data, flexibility, robustness, and user-friendliness. It excels in complex, dynamic systems and can be adapted to various objectives, making it a valuable tool for control and decision-making in diverse real-world applications.

A Fuzzy Controller is a mathematical controller designed to manage dynamic systems. It consists of three main components: the input stage, the processing stage, and the output stage. The input stage, fuzzification, reads analog signals from sensors—such as pressure, sound, and temperature—or digital signals, such as ON/OFF switches, and converts them into membership functions. The processing stage, the most critical component, is designed based on experimentation. In this stage, the controller's rules are generated and then translated to the output stage of the fuzzy controller. The final stage, defuzzification, converts the analyzed results into specific output values. (Dernoncourt, 2013). A fuzzy logic system is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Overview diagram of a fuzzy logic controller

Source: (Dernoncourt, 2013)

Fuzzification of input converts crisp (exact) input data into fuzzy values. Fuzzy logic systems operate with linguistic variables, representing input and output values using terms such as 'low,' 'medium,' and 'high' rather than precise numerical values. Fuzzification is the initial step in the fuzzy logic control process. It involves mapping crisp input values to fuzzy sets or membership functions that determine the degree to which each linguistic term applies.

Fuzzy rules are established to control the output. These rules in fuzzy logic are simple and follow an if-else structure, consisting of a condition and a corresponding target.

Defuzzification is converting a fuzzy logic controller's fuzzy, linguistic output into a specific numerical value that can be used for decision-making or system control. This step ensures that the fuzzy results are actionable in real-world applications.

2 Literature Review

The paper discusses the challenges of creating a standardized representation for automated planning in complex domains. It highlights that human modeling often becomes a bottleneck that limits the applicability of planning algorithms to real-world problems. It emphasizes the need for representations compatible with neural network processing without further transformation.

The authors present three different grid representations that effectively model a variety of classical planning problems. They analyze classical planning benchmarks to identify domains aligning with these proposed representations and demonstrate that even domains not originally defined on a grid can be adapted to a grid format with minor, domain-specific modifications. (Urbanovská & Komenda, 2022)

The study examines the limitations of existing path-planning algorithms, notably the A* algorithm and the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) algorithm, in generating smooth trajectories that adhere to the manoeuvrability constraints of mobile robots. It highlights that the RRT algorithm exhibits stochastic behaviour, often yielding inconsistent results across different applications, which can result in suboptimal paths for real-time operations due to its high computational overhead. Previous research has sought to enhance the A* algorithm by

modifying its search strategies, such as reducing the number of neighbouring node evaluations through slope detection techniques. However, these modifications have not sufficiently addressed the challenges related to path smoothness and computational efficiency. The proposed Generalized Wavefront Algorithm aims to generate smoother and more computationally efficient paths around obstacles to overcome these limitations. (Wu et al., 2020)

The paper compares the newly developed Bresenham-based Global Path Planning (BRP) algorithm against existing methods, including the Bug family of algorithms and classical approaches such as A*, D*, and Dijkstra. It highlights the performance differences, particularly improvements in path planning time for specific map configurations. Additionally, the study addresses the Piano Mover's problem, demonstrating that while the BRP algorithm enhances efficiency in path planning, it results in a marginal increase in route length—approximately 0.43% above the optimal path. This finding suggests potential areas for further optimization in motion planning tasks. (Velikzhanin & Skarga-Bandurova, 2023)

The literature review examines various approaches in path planning algorithms, including heuristic methods, the Wavefront Method, Genetic Algorithms, and Neural Networks. It highlights commonly used techniques such as artificial potential fields and D algorithms, demonstrating the diversity of strategies within the field. Furthermore, the review categorizes path planning algorithms based on the availability of environmental data, distinguishing between static and dynamic path planning. Static path planning assumes complete prior knowledge of obstacles, enabling preprocessing of the environment map. In contrast, dynamic path planning relies on real-time sensor data, operating with only partial information about obstacles in advance. (Kwon et al., 2006)

The wavefront-based motion planning approach has been widely utilized for mobile robot navigation. It was initially developed to propagate distance within a tessellated space from object boundaries toward their centers while analyzing shapes in 2D images. This algorithm is recognized for its simplicity and computational efficiency, particularly in navigating robots within fixed-size cell arrays. Additionally, the Modified Vector Field Histogram (M-VFH) method enhances the conventional VFH algorithm by offering a more detailed spatial representation of environments with densely cluttered obstacles. By employing a polar histogram divided into sectors, the M-VFH method effectively mitigates sensor inaccuracies. It reduces real-time data processing requirements, enabling smoother navigation and shorter path trajectories for mobile robots. (Luo, Krishnan, Paulik, & Jan, 2014)

The paper examines the efficiency of the wavefront path planning algorithm, a widely used method for mobile robot navigation, emphasizing its dependence on full wave expansion, which can be computationally expensive in large-scale environments. In contrast, the study introduces the modified wavefront algorithm, which enhances path planning efficiency in static environments by optimizing the selection process for the shortest path through an alternative value assignment strategy based on cell location. Furthermore, the research classifies robot path planning into two models: one with complete information, where the robot possesses full environmental knowledge and can execute offline planning, and another with incomplete information, where the robot relies on real-time sensory feedback to construct a global model for continuous online path planning. This distinction underscores the diverse methodologies and challenges associated with mobile robot navigation, contingent upon the availability of environmental data. (Tang et al., 2014)

The authors discuss the limitations of conventional occupancy grid maps in off-road environments, highlighting that impossible areas include obstacles and natural landscapes such as ramps and pits, which necessitates a new approach to path planning in outdoor navigation. It builds upon the D* search algorithm. It incorporates a hybrid vision system combining stereo

vision and omnidirectional vision to create 2.5D and 2D grid maps, allowing for a more efficient and robust path planning method that accounts for terrain characteristics like height difference, slope, and roughness. (Gu & Cao, 2009)

This research explores the application of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms, specifically Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) and Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), for path planning in dynamic and heterogeneous environments. Given the challenges posed by traditional path-planning methods in complex settings, the effectiveness of DRL in enabling adaptable and dynamic navigation solutions is assessed. Extensive simulations are conducted to compare the performance of DDQN and DDPG across various scenarios, emphasizing their respective advantages and limitations. While DDQN exhibits higher efficiency in static environments, DDPG is more effective in dynamic conditions due to its adaptability and continuous action capabilities. The findings provide valuable insights into the application of DRL in robotic navigation, particularly in unpredictable and diverse environments. Additionally, this study enhances the understanding of DRL in complex path-planning scenarios. It offers practical guidance for implementing these algorithms in real-world autonomous systems, contributing to advancements in the field of robotics. (Tabakis & Dasygenis, 2024)

This study introduces an innovative path planning algorithm based on Q-learning to identify multiple collision-free paths across three distinct dynamic environment maps with varying obstacle densities. Achieving optimal path planning in dynamic environments with numerous obstacles necessitates the development of virtual environment maps and the application of the Q-learning algorithm. The generated optimal paths in different environments are analyzed, supplemented by Q-values at the starting point. Additionally, training progress is visualized through graphs that track state rewards over multiple episodes. Experimental results confirm the algorithm's ability to successfully determine multiple optimal paths in dynamic environments and reach predefined target points. Future research will focus on enhancing the convergence rate in complex environments, offering significant potential for practical applications. (Luo et al., 2014).

3 Methodology

This section explains the main components used in this paper and briefly introduces the fuzzy controller. Key areas covered include differential mobile robots, wavefront-based path planning, and MATLAB®.

3.1 Differential Mobile Robot

The differential robot is the most common robot used to study various robotic algorithms (Hentout et al., 2022). It considers a wheeled type of robot, and it has two wheels, each wheel independently controlled. Its name refers to the fact that the motion sides of the robot are the sum of the independent wheel motion.

The drive wheels are usually placed on each side of the robot's body and toward the front, as shown in Fig. 5. The kinematic model analyzes the linear velocity and the angular velocity over time.

The linear and angular velocities can control this robot's path planning. In the kinematic model, the robot is modeled as a rigid body on wheels operating on the horizontal X-Y plane.

The robot is presented in a three-dimensional plane, and the two vectors for its position in the plane and one for orientation along the vertical axis are orthogonal to the plane. (Filipescu et al., 2011)

Fig. 5: The kinematic model of differential drive robot

Source: (Trajectory-tracking and discrete-time sliding-mode control of wheeled mobile robots,2011)

The main problem in the mobile wheeled robots, which many studies concentrate on, is localization. An encoder sensor is usually used to transduce rotation motion into a digital signal and feedback to the controller. There are two main types of this sensor which are absolute and incremental.

The output of an absolute encoder shows the current shaft position, making it an angle transformer. The output of an incremental encoder indicates information about the motion of the shaft, which typically is processed elsewhere into data such as position, speed, and distance (Murray, 2021).

An algorithm is a powerful mathematical solution for many problems and tasks nowadays (Yang, 2021). Some of these algorithms, which are fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, optimization algorithm, path planning algorithm, motion navigation algorithm, are used in mobile (Pandey, 2017). One of these algorithms is a dead reckoning that uses estimates a relative position from the initial starting point information.

This algorithm does not depend on any external signals and just only uses an inertial measurement unit (IMU) or a control variable, such as an encoder.

The dead reckoning algorithm operates with the global positioning system (GPS), ultrasonic local positioning systems, infrared network systems, radio frequency identification (RFID) systems, just in order to measure the position (Pandey, 2017).

The mathematical model of a wheeled robot with two controllable wheels as shown in fig.5 . This robot needs only a linear V and angular ω velocities, which are controlled by the

Fuzzy logic controller, to maneuver any differential drive robot in a plane. By controlling these velocities, an algorithm is applied to find the path to move in the plane.

Fig.5 shows the differential drive robot layout, where V_r is the velocity of the right wheel, V_l is the velocity of the left wheel, L is the distance between the center of the wheels, θ is the directional angle of the robot with respect to the reference coordinate system and r is the radius of the wheel. The linear velocity of the robot is the average of the individual wheel velocities and is given by

$$V_{linear} = \frac{v_r + v_l}{2} \quad (1)$$

the kinematic model of a robot is a mechanical way to present the motion equation of the robot in reference coordinate frame without any consideration to the dynamic components such as masses and forces. The inputs of the robot system required for a mobile robot are the linear V and angular ω velocities which are polar coordinates.

The kinematic equations are used to transform these inputs to rectangle coordinate (x, y) system which is the rate of change of position of the robot in the x -direction is \dot{x} . and that in the y -direction is \dot{y} . are given by

$$\dot{x} = V * \cos(\theta) \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{y} = V * \sin(\theta) \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega = \frac{v_r - v_l}{2} \quad (4)$$

Substituting the linear velocity V from equation (1), in equations (2) and (3), modifies \dot{x} and \dot{y} as,

$$\dot{x} = \frac{v_r + v_l}{2} * \cos(\theta) \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{y} = \frac{v_r + v_l}{2} * \sin(\theta) \quad (6)$$

The velocity V of the robot in a fixed reference coordinate system is therefore given by

$$V = \sqrt{\dot{y}^2 + \dot{x}^2} \quad (7)$$

Also, the velocity of each wheel in the robot can be calculated by:

$$v_r = v + \frac{L}{2} * \omega \quad (8)$$

$$v_l = v - \frac{L}{2} * \omega \quad (9)$$

where L is the length between the two wheels. In fact, the \dot{x} , \dot{y} and $\dot{\theta}$ can be found by v_r and v_l . also, by integration these three components, the result will be the actual the actual position x , y and the actual orientation θ in the reference coordinate as given:

$$x = \int_{t_0}^t \dot{x} = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{v_r + v_l}{2} * \cos(\theta) dt \quad (10)$$

$$y = \int_{t_0}^t \dot{y} = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{v_r + v_l}{2} * \sin(\theta) dt \quad (11)$$

$$\theta = \int_{t_0}^t \dot{\theta} = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{v_r - v_l}{2} dt \quad (12)$$

By making this kinematic model of differential robot as close loop, the θ acts as feedback of the rotation to controller for adjusting the angular velocity ω and the encoder sensor as feedback of the linear velocity.

The encoder sensor is connected to the wheels shift and counts discrete number of ticks corresponding to the rotation of the wheel as given in equation:

$$\text{Number of wheel rotation} = \frac{\text{Total encoder Ticks}}{\text{Tick count per rotation}} \quad (13)$$

Tick count per rotation comes with encoder datasheet sensor. The number of wheel rotation will be transduced to distance by odometer. One wheel rotates one full rotation which is 360 degree and the wheel center would have travelled a distance equal to the circumference of the wheel this circumference is given by the formula:

$$1 \text{ rotation} = 1 \text{ circumference} = 2 * \pi * R \quad (14)$$

where R is the radius of the wheel, so the distance traveled will equal:

$$\text{Distance traveled} = \text{Number of wheel rotation} * 2 * \pi * R \quad (15)$$

Substituting the equation 13 from 15:

$$\text{Distance traveled} = \frac{\text{Total encoder ticks}}{\text{Tick count per rotation}} * 2 * \pi * R$$

This subsystem's input will be the total encoder ticks, and its output will be the traveled distance. However, this calculation will only be true in the differential robot's forwarding motion.

The robot has two independent wheels on the right and left sides. In the rotation, the velocity of one wheel will be slower than the other so that the true calculation will be as given:

$$\text{Total distance traveled} = \frac{\text{right wheel} + \text{left wheel}}{2} \quad (16)$$

Nevertheless, the angular velocity ω can be calculated by the feedback θ . The error is between the desired θ and the actual θ : $e(t) = \theta_{\text{desired}} - \theta_{\text{actual}}$ actual this error will be as the input of the Fuzzy controller and the output of the

The fuzzy controller will be angular velocity ω , and the function of $\tan 2d$ will be used to avoid erroneous orientation and to make θ in the range of $[\pi, \pi]$.

The atan2 function produces the output θ in the range of the four quadrants of the plane. It also helps to determine the sign and placement of the input angle in the right quadrant.

As the kinematic model of differential, the robot has the mathematical model and the mathematical model of feedback sensors. The fuzzy logic controller will be added to the overall system as shown in Fig. 6 and tuned to its parameters in the next section.

3.2 Model/simulation development

In this section, MATLAB[®] software environment has been used to model the differential robot by Simulink[™]. The Simulink[™] block diagram is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Model diagram of the Differential Mobile robot

Also, the robot motion has been simulated by MATLAB®coder, and the result has been presented in both MATLAB Simulink, as shown in Fig. 7, and MATLAB®coder.

Fig. 7: Robot visualization in MATLAB

Source: Own processing

3.3 Wave front-based path planning – grid representation:

Grid-based representation (as illustrated in Fig. 8) is a method employed in path planning to identify optimal and shortest paths for mobile robots. This approach enables efficient navigation of robotic systems toward their target destinations. The grid-based method, first proposed by W. E. Howden in 1968, discretizes the operational environment into uniform grid cells.

The core principle involves partitioning the workspace into discrete units, where each cell is assigned an environmental traversal cost during path planning. The resolution of the grid—defined by the size of each cell—directly influences obstacle representation accuracy. Smaller grid sizes yield higher precision in modeling obstacles and environmental features. However, finer resolutions increase computational complexity, as more cells require processing.

Conversely, larger grid sizes reduce computational load but compromise spatial accuracy. Excessive grid granularity may strain CPU resources and fail to guarantee optimal path solutions (see Create Custom Grid World Environments, MATLAB®).

Fig. 8: Grid representation

Source:(Create Custom Grid World Environments, MATLAB®)

Wave-front propagation is type of grid-based method in path planning algorithms, as shown in fig.9.

Fig. 9: Wave front-based example

Source: (Metric Path Planning - Algorithms (Planners), CS521)

The strategy of this method is to count the distance between the mobile robot and any point in the configuration space (Metric Path Planning - Algorithms (Planners), CS521).

Unlike visibility graph, Wave front propagation depends on Manhattan distance and chamfer to obtain the optimal path for the mobile robot [38].

Manhattan distance uses 4-sectors connection, as shown in Fig. 9, and only words within the axial neighbors. Chamfer distance is not the same as Manhattan distance. It was chosen to discover a more direct path than the Manhattan distance by diagonal neighbors.

The outages of Wave-front propagation are by handling any shape of the obstacles, for example (circle, square, etc.), the ability to search and find the exact given destination, and simplicity in coding and implementing.

However, the safety factor ratio in this method is low because the mobile robot moves beside the obstacles, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Manhattan distance calculation for 2D

Source:(Distance Metrics for Machine Learning,2020)

Also, more memories are used in the CPU depending on the resolution of the grid. As it can be seen in Fig. 11, the less the map grid, the faster will be the calculation of finding the shortest path.

Fig. 11: Modelling autonomous Mobile Robot

Source:(authors)

3.4 Fuzzy logic controller

In the fuzzy controller shown in Fig. 12, the initial step involves defining the controller's parameters, including inputs, outputs, and rules. The parameters were tuned manually to check the lower cost function and reach higher optimal output values. Error ranges were established for changing error in theta. As for error in theta, the range is maintained between [-10, 10] degrees, as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 14 shows the integration of error membership function. For the integration of error, the range is set between [-30, 30] degrees, with. The room temperature membership function is shown in Fig. 18.

Three conditions were defined for both error and the integration of error, encompassing "Negative," "Zero," and "Positive." Additionally, three conditions were defined for the output, including "Negative," "Zero," and "Positive." Subsequently, nine rules were generated, as displayed in Tab [1]. Finally, the output membership function angular speed is shown in Fig. 15.

Tab. 2: Table 1. Rules of the fuzzy controller

Error	∫ Error (t)		
	Negative	Zero	Positive
Negative	NE	NE	ZE
Zero	NE	ZE	PO
Positive	ZE	PO	PO

Source: (Authors)

Fig. 42: Design of fuzzy controller

System fuzzyrules: 2 inputs, 1 outputs, 9 rules

Source: (Authors)

Fig.13: Error of (Theta) Membership of the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Fig. 14: Integration Error of (Theta) Membership of the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Fig. 15: Output variable of the fuzzy controller (Angular velocity)

Source: (Authors)

3.5 MATLAB® Simulation

Fig. 16 illustrates the performance of a robot navigation system in an obstacle-filled environment. The left panel shows the planned path (red crosses) avoiding red rectangular obstacles and leading to the target point (yellow star).

The right panel depicts the robot's real-time motion in a maze-like environment, with the actual trajectory (blue dashed line) and the robot's position (blue circle).

Fig. 16: First scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Tab. 2: Test result for the first scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Test values	Analysis
Elapsed time for Algorithm is (Second)	1.084655
Distance to reach target point (Meter)	34
Elapsed time for robot motion is (Second)	237.1065498

Tab. 2 shows the algorithm's execution time (1.085 seconds), path length (34 meters), and motion time (237.107 seconds). The figure highlights the algorithm's efficiency and ability to navigate complex environments effectively.

Fig. 17: Second scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Tab. 3: Test result for the second scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Test values	Analysis
Elapsed time for Algorithm is (Second)	27.771225
Distance to reach target point (Meter)	56
Elapsed time for robot motion is (Second)	428.571095

Fig.17 and Tab. 3 highlight, the algorithm's execution time (27.771 seconds), path length (56 meters), and motion time (428.571 seconds). The figure underscores the algorithm's capability to handle more intricate navigation scenarios efficiently.

Fig. 18: Third scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Tab. 4: Test result for the second scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Test values	Analysis
Elapsed time for Algorithm is (Second)	1.625631
Distance to reach target point (Meter)	34
Elapsed time for robot motion is (Second)	239.343115

As shown in Fig.18 and Tab. 4, the algorithm's execution time (1.625631 seconds), path length (34 meters), and motion time (239.343115 seconds).

Fig. 19: Fourth scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Source: (Authors)

Tab. 5: Test result for the Fourth scenario of modelling the mobile robot

Test values	Analysis
Elapsed time for Algorithm is (Second)	0.995970
Distance to reach target point (Meter)	34
Elapsed time for robot motion is (Second)	239.343115

Fig.19 and Tab. 5 highlights key performance metrics: the algorithm's execution time (0.995970 seconds), path length (34 meters), and motion time (239.343115 seconds).

4 Result

The analysis of the robotic path planning and execution process highlights the algorithm's efficiency in computing optimal paths across various scenarios, with computation times ranging from under 1 second to approximately 28 seconds, depending on the complexity of the environment. The generated paths are typically optimized for distance, around 34 meters in most cases, except for more challenging scenarios, such as one with a 56-meter path. However, the robot's motion time is significantly longer, ranging from 237 to 428 seconds, due to physical constraints like speed limits and obstacle navigation challenges in real-world execution. This gap between algorithmic efficiency and motion execution indicates that while the algorithm effectively plans optimal paths, enhancements in the robot's physical performance and adaptability are necessary. Integrating a fuzzy logic controller into the system could address these challenges by dynamically adjusting the robot's speed and trajectory based on real-time sensor inputs, such as obstacle proximity and path curvature, enabling smoother and faster navigation. The fuzzy controller would also improve adaptability to dynamic environments, reducing delays caused by recalculations and optimizing motion time. This integration, combined with the robust path-planning algorithm, provides a solid foundation for future advancements in robotic navigation, particularly in complex and dynamic scenarios.

5 Conclusion and Future work

This paper tackled the complexities associated with path planning for Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) through the formulation of a kinematic model utilizing MATLAB®, alongside incorporating a Fuzzy Logic Controller to augment adaptability and operational performance. The executed path planning algorithm exhibited the capacity to produce safe and efficient trajectories within static environments characterized by diverse curvatures. Fusing fuzzy logic enhanced navigational capabilities by adapting to ambient conditions, thereby diminishing execution duration and improving overall operational efficiency. These results underscore the promise of synergizing robust algorithmic frameworks with intelligent control mechanisms to propel advancements in autonomous robotics for practical applications. In future work, the auto-tuning method will be applied to the fuzzy logic controller using genetic algorithms (GA), particle swarm optimization (PSO), or artificial neural networks (ANN). Applying this idea with auto-tuning for fuzzy controller will lead to a real-world application such as an intelligent auto-parking system for autonomous vehicles. This paper could be transferred into implantation or task prototype using an Arduino or Raspberry Pi embedded controller and a mobile robot. In the future, this study will help apply more different path planning algorithms, such as the potential field algorithm and the probabilistic road map algorithm, in MATLAB and the real world.

6 Resources

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